

THE MULTIFACED IMPEDIMENTS TO VOCABULARY ACQUISITION EXPERIENCED BY B1 LEVEL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This article investigates the challenges inherent in second-language vocabulary acquisition and explores effective pedagogical strategies, offering insights informed by scholarly perspectives.

INTRODUCTION

The acquisition of a second language, a process fraught with inherent complexities, presents unique hurdles, particularly in the realm of vocabulary development, where the seemingly simple task of expanding one's lexicon can become a significant obstacle for many learners. While some individuals may find vocabulary acquisition relatively straightforward, a substantial number encounter considerable difficulty, often attributable to flawed learning methodologies or insufficient self-motivation, a struggle exacerbated for non-native English speakers who grapple not only with comprehending the semantic range of novel vocabulary items but also with mastering their intricate orthography, phonology, and appropriate contextual application, thereby highlighting the multifaceted nature of the challenges inherent in second language acquisition.

Nation (2006) posits that a foundational vocabulary of 2,000-word families is necessary for basic L2 comprehension, expanding to 8,000-9,000-word families for activities such as reading newspapers or novels. Despite this, contemporary language learners often fail to prioritize vocabulary development due to the considerable challenges involved:

The extensive synonymy inherent within the English lexicon presents a significant pedagogical hurdle for language learners, forcing them to navigate a complex web of semantic nuances and contextual appropriateness, thereby inducing a considerable degree of apprehension and hesitancy in selecting the most fitting vocabulary item for any given situation.

Concurrently, the orthographic complexities frequently associated with longer English words often lead students to eschew such lexical choices in favor of simpler, more readily spelled alternatives, thus inadvertently limiting their expressive range and contributing to a potentially impoverished command of the language's expressive potential.

Individual learning styles vary considerably, with some learners thriving on visually rich materials while others face significant barriers to accessing necessary resources due to socioeconomic limitations; this disparity in access, often stemming from financial constraints within their families, can profoundly demotivate students, leading to feelings of

discouragement and ultimately impacting their commitment to language acquisition, often resulting in premature abandonment of their learning goals rather than confronting the underlying socioeconomic factors affecting their educational opportunities.

Apathy and a lack of diligence frequently impede vocabulary development, a phenomenon exacerbated by the pervasive influence of modern technology. The readily accessible convenience of mobile phone translation applications often leads students to prioritize expediency over the more cognitively demanding, yet ultimately more effective, practice of consulting traditional dictionaries; consequently, a shift from reliance on readily available digital translation tools towards the deliberate and sustained use of printed dictionaries would demonstrably enhance vocabulary retention and mastery. Moreover, the unpredictable nature of English pronunciation, where orthography and phonology frequently diverge, presents a significant challenge for learners with underdeveloped pronunciation skills. This discrepancy often generates anxiety and self-consciousness when speaking or reading aloud, leading students to avoid employing less familiar vocabulary items altogether, rather than risking mispronunciation and seeking clarification.

However, according to [Michael Graves], there are four components of an effective vocabulary program:

- Wide or extensive independent reading to expand word knowledge
- Instruction in specific words to enhance comprehension of context containing those words
- Instruction in independent word-learning strategies
- Word consciousness and word-play activities to motivate and enhance leaning.

The aforementioned obstacles to second-language acquisition, encompassing issues of resource scarcity, motivational deficits, and phonological insecurity, are demonstrably mitigated through consistent engagement with the target language, integrating newly acquired vocabulary into both written and oral communication; supporting this assertion, Webb's 2005 study, which contrasted vocabulary acquisition through sentence construction with rote memorization from word lists, revealed a statistically significant advantage for the sentence-writing approach, indicating a superior level of retention and comprehension. In conclusion, while the challenges inherent in second-language learning are substantial and multifaceted, unwavering determination and strategic learning approaches can effectively surmount these obstacles, rendering the difficulties ultimately surmountable.

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